

The problem of diminishing storage profits from arbitrage

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of battery energy storage system (BESS) deployment on BESS profitability in the European day-ahead electricity markets, focusing on France, Germany, and Italy in 2030. In detail, it investigates how BESS arbitrage profits vary by using a comprehensive European market model with Monte Carlo simulations to account for generation outages and climate variability. The findings reveal significant cannibalization effects as BESS deployment increases, particularly in the Italian market, while greater renewable energy penetration tends to increase BESS profits, partially offsetting the cannibalization effect. The analysis also highlights that increased renewable deployment shifts electricity price distributions toward zero, especially in Germany, while in France it increases the likelihood of nuclear power becoming the marginal power plant. These results suggest BESS investors may struggle to recover required investment costs unless additional revenue streams from ancillary services and capacity markets are secured or government subsidies are provided.

Introduction

Energy storage is a critical component in the transition towards net-zero carbon emissions, as it helps address the variability of renewable energy sources such as wind and solar, which are intermittent by nature. Solar power production fluctuates with daylight hours and cloud cover, while wind generation varies with weather patterns. Energy storage systems bridge this intermittency gap by capturing excess energy during peak production periods and releasing it when generation declines, thus providing more consistent power delivery despite variable inputs. Moreover, as the proportion of renewable energy in the electricity mix increases, maintaining grid stability becomes more challenging. Energy storage also functions as a stabilizing asset class by providing frequency regulation, voltage support, and other ancillary services that traditionally came from conventional power plants. These capabilities ensure reliable electricity delivery even with high renewable penetration. In its Ten-Year Network Development Plan (EntsoE, 2024), Entso-E estimates that 700 GW of solar and 500 GW of wind power will be deployed in Europe by 2030 and that 200 GWh of battery energy storage systems (BESS) will be built by that time.

This massive deployment of renewables and BESS raises the question of whether and to what extent it will affect electricity prices and, in turn, how this will translate into a change in BESS investment's profitability. This work investigates how the increase in renewable and BESS deployment will affect expected BESS profits from arbitrage in day-ahead markets in 2030, focusing on France, Germany and Italy.

Literature Review

Energy storage systems play a crucial role in integrating variable renewable energy (VRE) sources into electricity markets. As VRE penetration increases, it leads to the merit-order and cannibalization effects, reducing wholesale electricity prices and VRE value, respectively (López Prol & Schill, 2021). While energy storage can mitigate these effects and improve system flexibility, its profitability is influenced by various factors. Studies show that community storage systems are more economically efficient than household systems (Scheller et al., 2020). Despite these challenges, research indicates that storage revenues may increase in future energy transition scenarios, albeit with higher associated risks (Dumitrescu et al., 2024). The impact of VRE on storage profitability varies by region, with wind power generally showing positive effects in some markets (Spodniak et al., 2021). In particular, (López Prol & Schill, 2021) discusses the economics of variable renewable energy and electricity storage, including the merit-order effect, the cannibalization effect, and the role of electricity storage and other flexibility options in integrating high shares of variable renewable energy. It observes that storage and other flexibility options can help mitigate the cannibalization effect of VRE. (Baumgarte et al., 2020) present a conceptual framework to characterize business models of energy storage, examines which storage technologies can perform identified business models, and reviews the recent literature on the profitability of individual combinations of business models and technologies. They observe

that certain combinations of energy storage technologies and business models have already reached profitability. Still, this conclusion only applies to the most recently examined combinations or those that stack multiple business sources. In contrast, many technologically feasible combinations of energy storage technologies and business models have not been studied, indicating a need for further research to understand the profitability of energy storage fully.

Methods

To assess the profitability of BESS, a European market model has been developed to simulate the European day-ahead market coupling. The electricity network has been created using the reference Entso-E electricity grid and adding the planned expansion in 2030. Demand and generation capacity in each country have been obtained from the Pan-European Market Modelling Database (EntsoE, 2024). This includes generation from 13 different fuel types (geothermal, marine, run of river, biomass, waste, gas, hard coal, heavy oil, hydrogen, light oil, lignite, nuclear, and oil shale). To account for the stochasticity of wind and solar generation, a Monte Carlo approach has been adopted by building different scenarios to account for generation outages and climate variability. Climate influences our model inputs in three key ways: it affects hourly capacity factors for renewable energy sources (solar, on shore and offshore wind); determines energy inflow to hydroelectric basins (relevant for dam-based, pondage, open-cycle pumped-storage, and run-of-river plants); and impacts hourly electricity demand across countries. To properly account for pumped-storage and reserve-based hydro, the reservoir levels throughout the year have been modelled with a weekly resolution for dam-based hydro, daily for poundage, and hourly for both open-cycle and closed-cycle pumped storage. This model has been used to solve a market clearing problem for each Monte Carlo scenario to obtain the electricity market prices and the BESS charging and discharging patterns, which have been used to determine the BESS profit from arbitrage in the day-ahead markets.

Results

The results show that the amount of renewable and BESS deployed significantly affects storage profits. Figure 1 reports the profitability of storage from arbitrage in the day-ahead market in France, Germany, and Italy in 2030. The values of renewable and BESS labelled with 100% in the y-axis and x-axis, respectively, represent the amount of renewable and BESS deployment that EntsoE expects in Europe in 2030. The figure shows how the increase in BESS deployment reduces the BESS profitability (profit cannibalization), particularly in the Italian market. By contrast, the increase in renewable tends to increase BESS profits, countering this effect.

Figure 1 The Figure shows how the BESS profit per MWh installed capacity in France, Germany and Italy changes as the deployment of BESS and renewable increases

Figure 2 reports the distribution of electricity market prices in the day-ahead market in France, Italy, and Germany in 2030 for different levels of renewable penetrations, showing how the increase in renewable energy shifts the electricity price distribution towards zero, particularly in Germany. In France, this significantly increases the likelihood of nuclear power being the marginal power plant.

Figure 2 Distribution of electricity market clearing prices in the day-ahead in France, Italy and Germany in 2030 for different levels of renewable penetrations (the value of 100% represents the expected renewable deployment in 2030).

Conclusions

Our comprehensive analysis of Italy, France, and Germany across multiple climate and outage scenarios provides compelling evidence that battery energy storage system technologies face significant cannibalization challenges on Europe's path to net zero, though with varying degrees of severity. These results show that BESS profitability in day-ahead markets can be significantly affected by the amount of BESS present in the market. This suggests that storage investors may find it difficult to recover the required investment costs to reach net zero carbon emission unless additional revenues are earned from different market streams (such as ancillary services and capacity markets) or through subsidies. These findings carry important implications for both investors and policymakers. To maintain the economic viability of BESS technologies, incentive schemes may require thoughtful design and periodic revision. The diminishing returns observed through cannibalization effects suggest that market design and policy frameworks should adapt dynamically as deployment scales up, ensuring continued investment in these essential technologies throughout the transition to net zero.

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